

CORRELATES OF HUNGER SEVERITY AND FOOD INTAKE AMONG RURAL HOUSEHOLDS IN NIGERIA: FACING THE KEY CHALLENGES OF THE 21ST CENTURY

Abiodun Olusola Omotayo¹

North West University, Mafikeng Campus, South Africa

Abstract

Nutritional deficiency and hunger are long-standing challenges in the developing nations where majority of people suffer from one of the heaviest burdens of hunger and malnutrition. Interventions aimed at increasing food availability and hunger reduction hold great potential for improving nutrition status through increasing food production in a developing nation such as Nigeria. We present a novel approach to explain the correlates of hunger severity and food intake among the rural households in Nigeria. Indicators of hunger severity and food intake were computed with coping options due to hunger and dietary diversity scores. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (percentage, standard deviation etc.) and inferential statistics, such as Principal Component Analysis (PCA), and Ordinary Least Square Regression (OLS). In the study, the descriptive results show that the rural respondents captured in the survey were 81.19% male, with an average age (53 ± 11.44 years) and (9.20 ± 4.83 years) of education. On the other hand, the regression results of the factors that affect the households' hunger severity and the composite food intake diversity indices (generated from the PCA) were well fitted ($p < 0.01$). Ageing, large household size and poor credit facilities, among others were identified as major problems among the rural dwellers. It was therefore concluded that hunger and poor diversity of food intake among the rural households were problems in the study area. It was however recommended that considerable investment in rural household's human capital should be encouraged since nutrition education and food diversity enhances households' wellbeing.

Keywords: *Dietary diversity scores, Food intake, Hunger severity index, Ordinary Least Square Regression, Principal Component Analysis, 24 Hours Recall Period.*

¹ omotayoabiodun777@gmail.com

1. Introduction

The 2017 Global Hunger Index (GHI) unveils the long-term progress in hunger reduction around the globe, even though the advances have been uneven, however, with millions of people still experiencing chronic hunger and many places suffering acute food crises and famine (von Grebmer Klaus et al., 2017). The state of the balance-global hunger situation especially in the developing nations of the world remains a cause for great concern which still constitutes a significant challenge for international commitments if “end hunger” must be realistic by 2030. According to United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF); World Health Organization (WHO) & World Bank (WB), (2017), an estimated 6 million children, under 5 years of age in the developing nations are stunted by chronic malnutrition.

About one in eight people, or 13.5 percent of the overall population, remain chronically undernourished in these developing regions of the world, down from 23.4 percent in 1990–92 (FAO et al., 2015). In year 2016, the number of undernourished people in the world was stated to increase to an estimated 815 million, up from 777 million in 2015 but still down from about 900 million in the year 2000 (Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO), International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD), United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), World Food Programme (WFP) and World Health Organization (WHO), 2017). In addition, the existing record have it that the vast majority of hungry people in the world live in developing regions, which saw a 42 percent reduction in the prevalence of undernourished people between 1990–92 as well as 2012–14 (International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI), 2017).

Nigeria, according to (The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), 2012) is a developing nation as well as Africa’s wealthiest, most populous nation still suffers one of the highest level of chronic hunger and under nutrition among its citizens. This crisis is largely caused by poverty and rising food insecurity, the disruption of basic services due to conflict, and poor knowledge of healthy feeding practices for infants and young children. In Nigeria, hunger, linked to poverty is a condition that reflects in the inadequacies to obtain food; this made the nation share in the severity, depth and incident with other developing nations hunger or poverty.

On the hand, the manifestations of hunger are sometimes overt, but are often invisible, and reflect the powerlessness and vulnerability of those who suffer from its consequences (World Food Programme, 2007).

Furthermore, hunger caused by an inadequate or inconsistent food supply at home is part of a larger societal issue that is variably referred to as “food poverty”, or “food insufficiency” (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), 1996) as cited by Pickett et al., 2015). These terms further refer to a myriad of situations where consistent physical and economic access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food of a person’s preference cannot be assured (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, 1996). Many at times, these largely hidden and seldom resulting in overt signs of malnutrition, “first-world hunger” (Riches 1998; Beebout, 2006), requires different observational methods to detect, measure and correct.

This study seeks to add to existing body of knowledge by analyzing the correlates of hunger severity and the determinants of food intake among the rural households in Nigeria. The study is different from previous studies because it used Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to construct indices of hunger severity and food intake as well as relating these with some socio economic, environmental and health indicating variables. The study is also justified from the robustness and representativeness of the employed primary dataset. The study therefore presents recommendations that aim to redress the national imbalances in term of hunger and food availability, as well as the laws, policies, attitudes, and practices that exacerbate and perpetuate them, in order to alleviate hunger among the rural most vulnerable individuals. The final section of this study discusses the implications of these findings for timely policy and research priorities.

2. The Policy Context for Rural Household’s Hunger and Food intake in Nigeria

Nigeria rural food intake and nutrition policies have undergone changes especially after her independent. This is because these policies and programmes vary only in terms of name, time or season cum organizational network of the then incumbent. All the way, the past policies have

emphasized almost the same objectives such as: to provide food for the inhabitants of the nation and export excess to other countries as well as to provide rural dwellers and farmers with extension services, agricultural support, rural development services and general sustainability. Despite the past policies and laudable programmes with impressive themes, Nigeria is yet to attain food sufficiency for households' intake, most especially in the rural settings of the nation where majority of food production takes place.

For example, between the 1960's -1990's, very few agricultural policies, decree and act existed with invention of numerous agricultural programmes like National Accelerated Food Production Programme (NAFPP) in 1972), Operation Feed the Nation (OFN in 1976). In addition, the Agricultural Development Projects (ADP), River Basin Development Authorities (RBDA in 1976), Green Revolution (GR in 1980) , Directorate for Food Roads and Rural Infrastructure (DFRRI in 1986) ,Better Life Programme (BLP in 1987), Family Support Programme (FSP in 1994) , Family Economic Advancement Programme (FEAP in 1996) and National Agricultural Land Development Authority (NALDA) which was initiated in 1992 much more later than the decree (1978) and an act (1979) backing it.

However, these past policies and programmes as earlier listed have contributed little or nothing to the long run agricultural sustainability, food intake and nutrition of the populace in Nigeria with this stake holders i.e the rural household's bearing majority of the brunt hence, these policies could be characterized as weak agricultural policy with non-interaction between and among stakeholders, short duration, conflicts each other, inconsistent and incompatibility. There is urgent need to reverse this lingering situation so as to ameliorate the persistent failure of agricultural, food intake and nutrition policies and programmes in Nigeria. Therefore, eliminating hunger as articulated in the national policy on agriculture, the Vision 2020, and the Millennium Development Goals, especially MDG 1 on hunger and poverty requires stimulation by policymakers, who should create an environment in which the rural households' food intake can thrive. Therefore, in line with the Vision 2020, and the Millennium Development Goals, especially MDG 1 policy guidelines, the agricultural policy of Nigeria aim to secure a conducive environment for these rural dwellers.

The evidence-based information on the nature and constraints to financing agricultural adventure by this farmers due to poverty as well as lack or partial provision of basic agricultural incentives cannot be under estimated for the design of appropriate strategies for reducing the vulnerability of these farming households' to poverty. As a developing nation, Nigeria advocates the integration of diversified food intake and nutrition into rural development programmes in order to alleviate the rural household's poverty stigma. Therefore, to inform the design for the holistic food intake-nutrition policy strategies, this study provides key insights into a national agricultural policy that are prioritized by these rural households. This information will serve as a strong basis for aligning government's agricultural blue prints with the rural scale dwellers as a center of consideration. Moreover, the evidence-based information on structural constraints to rural households' diversified food intake and nutrition in the selected rural parts of Nigeria forms an important basis for timely policy intervention.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Study Area and Data Description

Nigeria is the most populous country in Africa (The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), 2012). Some working projections have indicated that the country's population will increase from 140 million in 2006 (National Population Commission (NPC), 2006) to 204 million by 2020 (OECD, 2012). The country comprises of 36 states and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), (as indicated in Figure 1). These states are sub-divided into six geopolitical zones which are the North West, North East, North Central, South West, South East and South South. The country is made up of several ethnic groups although the Hausas, Igbos and Yoruba's are the major groups. Currently, the country is ranked as the second largest economy in Africa (National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), 2016).

The household survey data used for this analysis were collected in Nigeria around October 2014-February, 2015. The recall period for all rural household data used included the previous rainy and dry season's agricultural year. In order to observe the determinants of agricultural

household's food intake and hunger severity correlates, data were collected from a random selection of rural farming households. 18 villages were randomly selected, within these villages; individual households were randomly selected, conditional on agricultural practice as main source of income. Four hundred and twenty (420) households were then randomly selected from 18 villages using a proportionate sample. The identification of agricultural households and farming households was done in consultation with agricultural extension agents in the identified villages. The administered household survey questionnaire contained modules on socio-economic characteristics, food intake, nutrition, cost implication of nutrition.

(Figure 1)

3.2 Principal Component Analysis–Ordinary Least Square Regression Model Estimation

3.2a Composite Indices of the Rural Household's Food Intake and its Correlates

Principal Components Analysis (PCA) was used to compute the composite indices of food intakes from the different food classes that the questionnaire probed into. This approach helps capture the different dimensions of food that were consumed by households (within the 24 hours recall period) in a composite manner bearing in mind the likely correlation that could exist among some food classes . The selection of the indicator was guided by insights drawn from the nutrition literature as well as availability of data. All the major dimensions of nutrition (body's dietary needs) have been represented by at least one indicator. Following the identification of the indicators as explained above, the PCA was employed. The PCA is a data reduction method used to re-express multivariate data in fewer dimensions. The procedure transforms the selected indicators into smaller components that capture most of the information (variation) in the original indicators.

Application of PCA on the selected indicators would yield a series of components with the first component explaining the largest variance in the data and subsequent components explaining additional but smaller proportion of the variance in the original variables. Using the factor scores from the first principal components as weights, a dependent variable can then be constructed for each household, which has a zero-mean and variance equal to one. It is this dependent variable that can be regarded as households' food nutrition index. Accordingly, our dependent variable (PCA-based household food intake index) was generated. The variables selected for constructing the food index were the 12 food categories stated in the questionnaire which were coded as 1 if yes and 0 otherwise. These major food were grouped according to the FAO cereals, fish and sea food, root and tubers, pulses/legumes/nuts, vegetables, milk and milk products, fruits, oil/fats, meat, poultry and offal, sugar/honey eggs, miscellaneous. In order to provide a simple measure of the aggregation of the food component into food index (which on STATA was done with the command, `pca`, cereals, fish and sea food, root and tubers etc after which the command `Predict` food index was used and the index was computed as follows:

$$FOOD\ index = \phi_i + \beta_i \sum_{n=1}^c N_{ir} + z_v \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where food index is the Composite food Index, ϕ_i , β_i represents that parameters to be estimated. However, N_{ir} represents the vector of independent variables coded as cereals (yes=1,0 otherwise), fish and sea food (yes=1,0 otherwise), root and tubers (yes=1,0 otherwise), pulses/legumes/nuts (yes=1,0 otherwise), vegetables (yes=1,0 otherwise), milk and milk products (yes=1,0 otherwise), fruits (yes=1,0 otherwise), oil/fats (yes=1,0 otherwise), meat (yes=1,0 otherwise), poultry and offal (yes=1,0 otherwise), sugar/honey eggs (yes=1,0 otherwise), miscellaneous (yes=1, 0 otherwise) and z_v represents the error term. Using the index generated by PCA as the dependent variable, the Ordinary Least Square regression model was estimated as follows: Ordinary Least Square regression model was employed for the composite indices of food intakes and its Correlates i.e proxy for food intake. The Ordinary Least Square regression model is stated as:

$$Y = f(X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4, X_5, X_6 \dots \dots X_{10}, e_i) \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

“Y” is the generated food index of respondents while the independent variables “X’s” included were educational status of the head (number of educational years (continuous); type of agriculture practiced (1= crop planting/forestry,0=Otherwise); household heads' age (number of years (continuous); tribe of the head (1=Yoruba,0=otherwise); working class number (The total

number productive population within the households (continuous); total cost of feeding total value in Naira (continuous); total revenue (total value in Naira (continuous); net returns total value in Naira (continuous); households' dependency ratio the ratio of the dependent population to the total productive population within the households (continuous); possession of means of transport (dummy, 1 if yes , 0 if otherwise); financial source (dummy,1 personal savings, 0 otherwise); households' water purity (self-rated) (1 =Yes, 0= otherwise); households other source of income (dummy, 1 if yes , 0 if otherwise); total health cost (total value in Naira (continuous) and yield (in kilogram per hectares (continuous) while “ei” represents the error term.

3.2b Determinants of Hunger Severity Indices

The variables selected for constructing the hunger severity index were the 7 coping options categories (sales of assets, borrowing, drawing savings, reduction of production, adjustment of food intake, remittance and scavenging) highlighted in the questionnaire and described below. The variables selected for constructing the food index were coded as 1 if yes and 0 otherwise, In order to provide a simple measure of the aggregation of these coping mechanism into Hunger severity index (which on STATA was done with the command, pca sales of assets, borrowing, drawing savings, reduction of production, adjustment of food intake, remittance and scavenging, after which the command Predict food index was used. The index was computed as follows:

Where hunger index is the Composite food Index, D_i and β_i represents the parameters to be estimated. However, X_{ir} represents the vector of independent variables coded as sales of assets (yes=1,0 otherwise), borrowing (yes=1,0 otherwise),drawing savings (yes=1,0 otherwise), reduction of production (yes=1,0 otherwise), adjustment of food intake (yes=1,0 otherwise), remittance (yes=1,0 otherwise) and scavenging (yes=1,0 otherwise) and z_0 represents the error term. Using the index generated by PCA as the dependent variable, the Ordinary Least Square regression model was estimated as follows:

$$Z = f (X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4, X_5, X_6 \dots X_{12}, q_i) \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

“Z” is the generated food index of respondents while the independent variables “X’s” included were gender of the households head (dummy;1 if head is male,0 if female) ; marital status of the head (dummy;1 if married,0 otherwise); number of households working class (number of members (continuous); household heads’ age (number of years (continuous); tribe of the head (1= Yoruba ,0 = others); year of education of the head (number of educational years (continuous); alcoholism habit (dummy, 1 if yes, 0 if otherwise); existence of environmental problem (dummy, 1 if yes, 0 if otherwise); total cost of health (total value in Naira (continuous); total farm revenue (total value in Naira (continuous); households water purity (self-rated) (dummy, 1 if yes, 0 if otherwise); farming experience (years of farming); eating outside family food plan (dummy, 1 if yes, 0 if otherwise); knowledge of nutrition (dummy, 1 if yes, 0 if otherwise) while “qi” represents the error term.

4. Result and Discussion

4.1. Socio-Economic Characteristics of the Respondents

Several socio-economic indicators affect household’s food intake and hunger . The pertinent explanatory variables in these analysis are presented in Table 1,2 and 3. These explanatory variables were developed, based on previous food intake and hunger severity literature (Garrett and Ruel 1999; Hall et al., 2012; Regmi and Paudel, 2017). Respondents were asked several questions related to the socio-economic make up of their households, including gender of household head, (a dummy variable: 1 = male and 0 = female), age of household head (in years), and the number of household members with secondary education or higher. Table 1 shows that the average age of the respondents in the study was 53 years with a standard deviation of 11.44. This shows that the household heads were ageing which is in line with the findings of (Ello-Martin et al., 2007; Lee, 2010; Miller, 2014 and Ganiyu and Omotayo, 2016).

In addition, the mean household size of 6.21 (this could be interpreted as 7 since we are dealing with human beings). Although, large household size could be said to be based on a personal view of interest as an increase in households size increases expenditure and this, in turn, decreases farmers’ income (Ali and Ahmad, 2013). Large household size could lead to correspondingly poor food intake and health in the study area. Also, FAO (2014), opined that larger household

size exacerbates poverty levels. Gender result further reveals that 81.19% of the respondents were male. This finding is in line with the belief that rural households' head is predominantly male oriented. The marital status configuration of the study indicates that 74.52% of the respondent were married, this can positively influence households' nutrition, and hence agricultural outcomes as the wife(s) and children will help in cooking activities thereby enhancing the farmer's devotion to his farming activities. The family member, the wife and the children can also join and assist on farm, thereby serving as a good source of labour. This confirms earlier findings by various researchers (Titus et al, 2015).

Furthermore, the mean years of education of 9.2 years was derived in the study. This by implication implies that higher number of educational years could have a positive influence on the ability of the rural dwellers to know their nutrition composition of food and the need for diversity (Contento, 2007; Godfray et al, 2010). Finally, the distribution of respondents according to credit accessibility as shown below indicates that most of the respondents, 54.05% were without access to credit. This shows that larger percentage of the respondents are still credit constrained and they might have to continue to plough their limited capital year after year hence, a low output which will invariably affect their farming returns and nutrition status.

(Table 2)

4.2. Food intake of Respondents

The distribution of respondents by the source of food in Table 2 shows the breakdown of various food components in the 12 food group eaten by the respondents in the study area. The Table shows that cereal, 78.81% and fat and oil 93.81% were the most consumed food within the 24 hours recall period of data collection as recommended by the (FAO, 2013).

(Table 2)

4.3. Respondents by Food Source

Table 3 shows that 37.86% of the farming households' usually obtain food from their self-farm. Other food sources identified in the study were the purchase of food, borrowing, food aid and

other sources. The fact that majority of the respondents eat from their self-farm across the selected states suggests that the rural dwellers are majorly small scale farmers with low agricultural output and returns. In addition, the distribution of respondents by the source of food across selected states is represented in Table 3, the result shows that 37.86% of the farming households' obtain food from their self-farm. Other food sources identified in the study were the purchase of food, borrowing, food aid and other sources. The fact that majority of the respondents eat from their self-farm across the selected states suggests that the South-west farmers are majorly small scale farmer with low agricultural output and returns.

(Tables 3)

Table 3 further shows the respondents' distribution according to daily food intake. A larger percentage of the farming households i.e. 40.95% eat twice daily. This could be because of the respondents are rural dwellers that lack adequate nutritional knowledge and or as result of their poor status decides to eat twice as a coping strategy, even the 2 meals eaten per day most likely lacks the appropriate nutritional contents. Poor food intake is a key factor that could lead to malnourished status (Nieuwenhuizen et al., 2010). Table 3 also shows the dietary diversity scores of the respondents. Households' dietary diversity score (HDDS) was based on 12 food groups as earlier mentioned. The mean score recorded was 4.87 as against the mean cut-off point of 6. This therefore indicates an inadequate household dietary diversity score (HDDS) in the rural communities. This is in line with existing literature. It has been shown in previous studies that increase in dietary diversity (food intake) is connected with households' food security status (i.e. households' energy availability) and socio-economic status (World Health Organization (WHO, 2000). More so, poor food intake may be as a result of lack of nutritional knowledge, cultural background and belief as most farmers in this part of Nigeria eat more of monotonous meals principally carbohydrate class than diversified diets needed for proper body nourishment. Poor dietary intake may be a contributing factor to malnutrition (Govender, 2016).

Finally, the respondents coping mechanism for food shortage explains that large percentage (34.76%) of the farming households adopt adjustment of food intake whenever they run out of food in their respective households. This signifies the presence of poverty in the study area as these respondents do not have enough to save during on-season while others resolve to coping

actions such as sales of asset, reduction of production inputs, remittances, scavenging. Therefore, to wrestle poverty, developing countries need good/sound health and sustainable agriculture since scanty output by farming households due to illness affects their return and further deepens their poverty level in all its dimensions i.e. poverty incidence, depth and severity (White, 2012; Omotayo 2016).

4.4 Estimates of the Correlates of the Farming Household's Hunger Severity Index

This section estimated the determinants of the farming households' severity of hunger in Nigeria using ordinary least square regression. High level of tolerance computed for the variables indicates that there was absence of serious multicollinearity in the analysis. In order to avoid inconsistency and biasness from the estimated parameters, the study subjected the variables to multicollinearity test using Collin command in STATA 13. Test for multicollinearity among the variables was carried out with variance inflation factor (VIF), the mean VIF of 1.15 was derived as indicated in Table 4. Since some of the variables included to capture the respondent demographic characteristics showed statistical significance, the null hypothesis is therefore rejected. Following the procedure earlier described, Principal Component Analysis was employed to construct the severity of hunger index at the farming households' level. Also, the Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test for heteroscedasticity was carried out after the regression and none of the degree of freedom for chi-squared test was significant so, the null hypothesis of heteroscedasticity is accepted. If it had been found heteroscedastic, there could have been need to estimate the robustness of the standard error.

Table 5 shows that five out of the fourteen variables in the analysis were significant. The variables that significantly affect the households' nutrition were household heads' age ($p < 0.10$), tribe of the head ($p < 0.10$), year of education of the head ($p < 0.01$), alcoholic habit ($p < 0.10$), households water purity ($p < 0.01$). While other variables such as gender of the households head, marital status of the head, ratio of the households working class, existence of environmental

problem, total cost of health, total farm revenue, farming experience, eating outside family food plan, knowledge of nutrition were statistically insignificant ($p > 0.10$). Table 5 shows that the parameter of the farming household heads' age was positive (0.0113) and significant ($p < 0.10$). This implies that if the household heads' age increases by one year, hunger severity index would increase by 0.0113 unit. This could imply that older age of the farming households head translate into reduced productive capacity hence, reduced income and increased severity of hunger. Good nutrition and avoidance of hunger contribute significantly to the health and wellbeing of older individuals, and to their ability to recover from illness (Forster and Gariballa, 2005; Hall et al. 2012).

(Table 4)

In addition, the parameter of the farming households' tribe was positive (0.4723) and significant ($p < 0.10$). This indicates that there is positive and direct relationship between being from Yoruba tribe of Nigeria and having good nutrition status (hunger severity index). This could be due to the fact that the region of the nation still remains a considerably educated region where an average household have basic knowledge of food and nutrition, this is in line with Myers and Painter (2017). On the other hand, the coefficient of respondents year(s) of education was negative (-0.0414) and significant ($p < 0.01$) in the model. It implies that if the households' heads educational level increases by one year, hunger severity index would decrease by -0.0414. However, this study does not posit in any way to downplay the importance of education in nutrition and health for evidence abound in the literature on the positive role education play in nutrition and health status and ability to attract higher income all over the world (Acker and Gasperini, 2009).

Furthermore, the dummy parameter of respondents, alcoholic habit was positive (0.8009) and significant ($p < 0.10$) with their hunger severity level. This implies that a unit increase in alcoholic consumption by the farming households would lead to 0.8009 unit increase in their hunger severity level. This is expected, as literature affirms that alcoholics often eat poorly, limiting their supply of essential nutrients and affecting both energy supply and structure maintenance thereby being unfit for economic activities that could bring in income hence hunger consequence. Furthermore, alcohol interferes with the nutritional process by affecting digestion, storage, utilization, and excretion of nutrients of the farming households (Leiber, 1988).

Expectedly, the farming households' parameter of self-rated water purity level captured in its dummy form was positive (0.3406) and significant ($p < 0.01$). This indicates that the farming households who drink/use pure water for consumption and other activities have higher likelihood of having good nutritional status and less hunger severity in the study area.

(Table 5)

4.5 Estimates of the Composite Diversity Indices of Food Intake and its Correlates

Following the procedure earlier described (See 3.2a), Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was employed to construct food intake index at the farming household level. Previous study by Demeke *et al.* (2011), used five variables as indicators. Accordingly, as described in the previous section, this approach is justified because cereals, fish and sea food, root and tubers, pulses/legumes/nuts, vegetables, milk and milk products, fruits, oil/fats, meat, poultry and offal, sugar/honey eggs, miscellaneous food consumed are all the food groups belonging to the key classes of food needed for proper nutrition (FAO *et al.* 2011; ACF International (2010). The 12 food groups were used to compute the food diversity index variable which was the dependent variable in the Ordinary Least Square regression (OLS). Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test for heteroscedasticity was carried out after regression and none of the degree of freedom for chi-squared test was significant. The null hypothesis of homoscedasticity was accepted. If it had been found heteroscedastic, there could have been need to estimate the robustness of the standard error.

In addition, in order to avoid inconsistency and biasness from the estimated parameters, the study subjected the variables to multicollinearity test using Collin command in STATA 13. Table 6 shows the test for multicollinearity among the variables, this was carried out with variance inflation factor (VIF), and the mean VIF was 1.10. Also, high level of tolerance computed for the variables indicates that there was absence of serious multicollinearity in the analysis. Obviously, since some of the variables that captured the socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents

showed statistical significance. This implies that the null hypothesis should be rejected. Table 7 shows the estimated parameters for the determinants of rural households' food intake in Nigeria using ordinary least square regression. Among the variables included in the analysis, type of agriculture practiced, working class number, net returns, households dependency ratio, possession of means of transportation, households' other source(s) of income, farm yield have significant positive or negative influence on households' food intake captured as their food index.

Type of agricultural practice being engaged by the rural households was statistically significant ($p < 0.10$) with a negative coefficient (-0.23721). This implies that there is indirect relationship between the agricultural households and their composite food diversity level in the study area. It means that those farmers that were growing crops had their composite food diversity indices being reduced by 0.23731, when compared with other farmers. This might be due to the small scale nature of cropping activities in the study area which leads to little returns to the crop planting households. Similarly, the parameter of the number of the working class among the household members is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) with positive sign (0.12848). This implies that as the number of working class members in a household increases, the composite diversity indices of food intake increased. This is expected because increase in the number of working members in a household would lead to increase in family income which would as well possibly influence food intake and its diversity. Similarly, the coefficient of household heads' net return/profit was statistically significant ($p < 0.10$) with a positive coefficient (0.23528). This indicates that respondents' net return have a strong positive relationship with their food diversity index. This is expected as households' are more likely to spend more money on food when they have better profit from their farming business. Kant and Graubard (2013), observed that both households' income and education contribute to differences in food intake patterns of low and high socio-economic status households.

In the same vein, the dependency ratio parameter (captured as the ratio of the dependent population to the total productive population within the households) of the farming households have a significant ($p < 0.05$) and positive (0.36500) effect on their composite food diversity. This indicates that if the farming households' dependency ratio increases by one individual,

composite food diversity would increase by 0.36500 unit. This is in line with the a priori knowledge as households' dependency ratio is supposed to affect their food intake level. A farming household with lower number of dependants will possibly have more access to more diversified food for consumption when compared with their counterparts in this same small scale farming adventure and with a larger dependants in the study area (Ndobo and Sekhampu, (2013); Aidoo *et al.* (2013). As expected, the parameter of assets possession captured with a possession of means of transportation (captured as 1 if yes and 0 otherwise) was positive (0.45974) and significant ($p < 0.05$). This implies that farming households that possesses asset(s) like bicycle or vehicle have better possibility of increasing their composite food diversity index. This is expected as possession of vehicle or bicycle (asset) indicates a better welfare of the farming households which might invariably reflect in improved food intake as against their counterparts without such assets. Moreover, assets possession is one of the major means of wealth accumulation in rural areas (Babatunde *et al.* 2011; Beyene and Muche, 2010).

Contrary to expectation, the parameter household head's possession of other source (s) of income had a negative (-0.25169) and significant coefficient ($p < 0.10$). This indicates that access to other source(s) of income aside their farming enterprise's revenue reduced households' composite food diversity index. This is not expected as non-farm enterprise has been confirmed in literature as good support for farming enterprise (Omotayo, 2016). In addition, the parameter of the farming households yield (Captured as in Kilograms per hectares) was positive (0.0000) and significant ($p < 0.10$) as expected. This means that farming households' food intake is a function of their farm yield. This indicates that the higher the households farm yield, the better their food intake level. This could be due to the fact that increase in farm yield leads to increase in the farming households' access to food and revenue which could invariably enhance the farming households' propensity to consume.

(Table 6)

(Table 7)

5. Conclusion

Poor food intake, malnutrition, and hunger are major problems of many rural households of developing nations. In Nigeria, these trio-threats constitute physical and economic problem by eating deeply into the financial base of the victims. This study, therefore, evaluated the hunger severity and food intake among rural households in Nigeria. The finding of the study concludes that farmers in the study are ageing; this is evidenced in the mean age of 53 years. Also, a large households' size was recorded in the research as the study recorded average of 7 in the study area, large household size could lead to corresponding hunger, poor food intake and nutrition in the study area. Furthermore, the mean years of education was 9.2 years, a higher number of years of education could have a positive influence on the ability of the farmers to know their nutrition composition of food and the need for food intake diversity. It can also enhance their knowledge of the association between food intake and nutrition.

The findings of this research emphasized the significance of educational attainment and large households' size as a contributor to farming households and nutrition in the study area. There is a serious need to enhance the knowledge/education of these rural dwellers on food intake diversity and nutrition issues. Family planning technique in relation to achieving a sustainable agricultural system through extension officers was identified due to the recorded family size in the study area. Rural households' possession of asset such as bicycle, vehicle and livestock were repeatedly significant to food intake and nutrition in the models. This indicates that rural households in Nigeria need financial support, in form of loan for their farming enterprise so that they can make better revenue and profit in order to possess assets since assets possession is an indicator of good welfare.

In addition, respondent water source was identified to be relevant to their health, this call for the need for the households' to be careful of the water they take while there is also need for good water sources in the study area. Finally, it was concluded that hunger severity among the ruralites was high and low diversity of food intakes was a major problem in the study. Farming household's capability to endure shocks like food insecurity was greatly determined by their respective asset portfolio such as financial, physical and human assets which are intangible. Food intake and nutrition of rural food households, therefore, must be seen as both consumption and

investments assets. Based on the findings of this study, the general conclusion is that hunger and poor nutrition are prevalent rural households of Nigeria. The findings further stressed the need for the government of the day to enhance the wellbeing of the rural households through capacity development and skill building programs.

6. Policy Recommendation

These results can serve as inputs for the development of evidence-based policy interventions to promote rural households food-nutrition, particularly in the rural areas of Nigeria, putting the rural households “the principal operators” perceptions and needs into account. The evidence of agricultural households’ vulnerability to poor food intake and nutrition was articulated previously in spite of the existing Nigerian national agricultural policies, signifies the importance of formulating at least workable region-specific policy strategies in order to achieve this national aim. This endeavor could invariably guarantee the appropriateness and more effectiveness of interventions which will steer up the support and uptake by the local stakeholders (such as the rural communities, rural households, agricultural extension expert, and Non-Governmental Organization etc). Based on the outcomes of this study, the following policy implication, and recommendations are made:

(1) Rural households’ were found to be ageing. The government of the day should encourage the young stars by implementing policies that will make agriculture more lucrative so that the ageing rural farmers can be replaced by the youths who are presently migrating to the urban areas.

(2) Education attainment is a key significant variable as it was emphasized in this study. It contributes to farming households’ food intake and nutrition status. It is therefore suggested that school enrolment should be encouraged and standard of education should be enhanced by the government of the day through extension agencies so that the rural dwellers will be knowledgeable about the importance of various food components and nutrition as well as their implication on the sustainable agricultural system.

- (3) Elimination of extreme hunger and poverty through enhancing agricultural productivity, credit and capital investment are identified to enhance farming activities in rural, Nigeria. The government should, therefore, provide standard loan acquisition systems, to facilitate access to credit.
- (4) The Large household size was also identified among the rural households in the study. There should be a proper orientation of rural households on family planning methods.
- (6) Food intake is an important pillar of food security. The rural households' should be enlightened on the various food classes and the need for a balanced diet. The various government administrators should mobilize nutritionists and trained agricultural extension officers to educate the rural household on the need to eat adequate meals.
- (7) Extreme hunger and poor nutrition was prevalent among the rural households in this study. There should also be more serious interventions by the government of consistent mobilization of resources, formulation, and implementation of holistic policies and programmes that will help out.

References

1. 2017 Global Hunger Index: The inequalities of hunger. Washington, D.C.; Bonn; and Dublin: International Food Policy Research Institute, Welthungerhilfe, and Concern Worldwide. <https://doi.org/10.2499/9780896292710>.
2. ACF INTERNATIONAL 2010. Food Security and Livelihood Assessments a Practical Guide
3. Acker, D. and Gasperini, L. 2009. Education for Rural People – The Role of Education, Training, and Capacity Development in Poverty Reduction and Food Security. *The Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations, Rome*.
4. Aidoo, R., Mensah, J. O., Tuffour, T. 2013. Determinants of household food security in Sekyere-Afram plains district of Ghana. Proceedings of the 1st Annual International Interdisciplinary Conference, AIIC 2013, 24-26 April. Azores, Portugal.

5. Ali, S. and Ahmad, N., 2013. Human capital and poverty in Pakistan: Evidence from the Punjab province. *European Journal of Science and Public Policy*, 11, 36-41.
6. Babatunde, R.O., Omotesho O.A. and Sholotan O.S. 2011 Socio-economic characteristics and food security status of farming households in Kwara State, North-Central Nigeria. *Pakistan Journal of Nutrition* 6(1), 49-58.
7. Beebout, H. S., 2006. Nutrition, food security, and obesity. *Gender Issues*, 23(3), 54-64.
8. Contento , I.R., 2007. *Nutrition education: linking research, theory, and practice*. Jones & Bartlett Learning.
9. Demeke, A.B., Keil, A. and Zeller, M., 2011. Using panel data to estimate the effect of rainfall shocks on small holders food security and vulnerability in rural Ethiopia. *Climatic change*, 108(1), pp.185-206.
10. Ello-Martin, J.A., Roe, L.S., Ledikwe, J.H., Beach, A.M. and Rolls, B.J., 2007. Dietary energy density in the treatment of obesity: a year-long trial comparing 2 weight-loss diets. *The American journal of clinical nutrition*, 85(6), pp.1465-1477.
11. FAO, IFAD, UNICEF, WFP and WHO. 2017. The State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World 2017. Building Resilience for peace and food security. Rome, FAO. Accessed in November 28th, 2017
12. FAO, IMF, & UNCTAD, 2011. the World Bank, the WTO, IFPRI and the UN HLTF (2011). *Price Volatility in Food and Agricultural Markets: Policy Responses*. Rome, FAO.
13. FAO/WFP 2014. The State of Food Insecurity in the World 2014: Strengthening the enabling environment for food security and nutrition ‘. Rome: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. <http://www.fao.org/3/a-i4030e.pdf>.(Accessed online on 19th December 2016).
14. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) 2013. Guidelines for measuring household and individual dietary diversity 2-12. http://www.fao.org/fileadmin/user_upload/wa_workshop/docs/FAO-guidelines-dietary-diversity2011.pdf.

15. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations., 1996. Rome Declaration on World Food Security and World Food Summit Plan of Action.
<http://www.fao.org/docrep/003/w3613e/w3613e00.htm>. Accessed November 2017.
16. Food and Agriculture Organization, International Fund for Agricultural Development, World Food Program. 2015. “The State of Food Insecurity in the World 2015. Strengthening the enabling environment for food security and nutrition.” Rome: FAO. For Field Workers Technical Department of Food Security and Livelihoods. ACF international. Retrieved from actionagainsthunger.org/sites/default/files/publications/acf-fsl-manual-final-10-lr.pdf (accessed on 8th December 2016).
17. Forster, S. and Gariballa, S., 2005. Age as a determinant of nutritional status: a cross sectional study. *Nutrition Journal*, 4(1), p.28.
18. Ganiyu, M.O. and Omotayo, A.O., 2016. Effects of Livelihood Activities on the Households’ Food Security in the Ogbomoso South Local Government Area of Oyo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Human Ecology*, 56(1,2) : 107-113.
19. Garrett, J. L., & Ruel, M. T. 1999. Are determinants of rural and urban food security and nutritional status different? Some insights from Mozambique. *World Development*, 27(11), 1955–1975.
20. Godfray, H.C.J., Beddington, J.R., Crute, I.R., Haddad, L., Lawrence, D., Muir, J.F., Pretty, J., Robinson, S., Thomas, S.M. and Toulmin, C., 2010. Food security: the challenge of feeding 9 billion people. *science*, 327(5967), pp.812-818.
21. Govender, L., Pillay, K., Siwela, M., Modi, A. and Mabhaudhi, T., 2016. Food and Nutrition Insecurity in Selected Rural Communities of KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa- Linking Human Nutrition and Agriculture. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 14(1), p.17.
22. Guyer, J.I., 1980. Food, cocoa, and the division of labour by sex in two West African societies. *Comparative Studies in Society and History*, 22(3), pp.355-373.
23. Hall, K. D., Heymsfield, S. B., Kemnitz, J. W., Klein, S., Schoeller, D. A., and Speakman, J. R. 2012. Energy balance and its components: implications for body weight regulation. *The American journal of clinical nutrition*, 95(4), 989-994.

24. Hall, K.D., Heymsfield, S.B., Kemnitz, J.W., Klein, S., Schoeller, D.A. and Speakman, J.R., 2012. Energy balance and its components: implications for body weight regulation. *The American journal of clinical nutrition*, 95(4), pp.989-994.
<http://www.fao.org/3/a-I7787e.pdf>.
<https://rd.springer.com/content/pdf/10.1007%2FBF03186777.pdf>. Accessed November 28, 2017.
25. International Food Policy Research Institute. 2017. 2017 Global Food Policy Report. Washington, DC: International Food Policy Research Institute.
<https://doi.org.10.2499/9780896292529>.
26. Kant A. K. and Graubard B.I. 2013. Family income and education were related with 30-year time trends in dietary and meal behaviors of American children and adolescents. *J Nutr*. 2013 May; 143 (5):690-700.doi; 10.3945/jn.112.165258.Epub 2013 Mar 20.
<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/23514763>.
27. Lee, M.R. and Berthelot, E.R., 2010. Community covariates of malnutrition based mortality among older adults. *Annals of epidemiology*, 20(5), pp.371-379.
28. Lieber, C.S., 1988. Biochemical and molecular basis of alcohol-induced injury to liver and other tissues. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 319(25), pp.1639-1650.
29. Miller, C.K., Kristeller, J.L., Headings, A. and Nagaraja, H., 2014. Comparison of a mindful eating intervention to a diabetes self-management intervention among adults with type 2 diabetes: a randomized controlled trial. *Health Education & Behavior*, 41(2), pp.145-154.
30. Myers, A. M., and Painter, M. A., 2017. Food insecurity in the United States of America: an examination of National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). Nigerian Gross Domestic Report. Abuja: National Bureau of Statistics; 2016. www.nigerianstat.gov.ng/download/518. Accessed 15 Apr 2016.
31. National Population Commission (NPC). Population and housing census in Nigeria. National Population Commission; 2006.
32. Ndobu, F. and Sekhampu, T. J. 2013. Determinants of vulnerability to food insecurity in South Africa Township: A Gender Analysis. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 4(4), 311-317.

43. White, B. 2012. Agriculture and the generation problem: rural youth, employment and the future of farming. *IDS Bulletin*, 43, 9-19.
44. WHO, 2000. A global agenda for combating malnutrition: progress report. Geneva. <http://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/66509>.
45. World Food Programme, 2007. World Hunger Series 2007: hunger and health. London: earthscan. http://www.wfp.org/sites/default/files/World_Hunger_Series_2007_Hunger_and_Health_EN.pdf. Access November 2017.